

ISic3575

Honours for Aviana

Language

Latin

Type

honorific (?)

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2019-07-10 - Jonathan Prag revised the file based on study for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated 1972, in room 7 of the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997856, 14.262463

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30596

Physical Description

A thin slab of cream-coloured marble with blue-grey veins. The stone is broken on the right side and at the bottom. The reverse of the stone shows signs of having been prepared for fixing in a wall or monument, as well as traces of mortar; there is a hole for a metal fixing on the top edge.

Dimensions

Height 58 cm

Width 44 cm

Depth 2.5-3 cm

Layout

Three lines of Latin text are preserved, but the end of each line is lost. Engraved guidelines for the layout of the text are visible for all three lines. The letters of all three lines are of approximately equal height (65-70 mm), although the second I in line 2 is extended to a height of 92 mm.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-3: 65-70 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. Avianiae · Av[---]
2. P(ubli) · Aelii · Ux[ori]
3. D(ecreto)) (vac.undefined) D(ecurionum)

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

(Set up) for Aviania Av[--?--], wife of Publius Aelius, by the decree of the town

council.

Commentary

The traces of the last letters visible at the end of each line are enough to identify them. The second name of Aviania cannot be guessed, but the only likely word at the end of line two is *uxor*, 'wife'. The abbreviation at the end of the text, DD, is standard, and also shows that this text belongs to the period when Halaesa was a Roman municipium (from the time of Augustus onwards). The original size of the inscription can be estimated from the central position of DD, and the stone was probably approximately 60cm wide originally, with only 4-5 letters missing from line 1, and 3-4 from line 2.

The gentilicium (family name) Avianius is known from Centuripe (ISic0005 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0005>]); it is not otherwise recorded in Sicily, although it is common in central and southern Italy. The name Aelius is a very common name, although not very frequent in Sicily; it is attested at Halaesa in the fragmentary text for Alfia (ISic3574 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3574>]) and in the Greek honorific for a rhetor (ISic3591 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3591>]).

It is likely that this text and the fragmentary text for Alfia were set up in honour of female members of the same family, since Alfia is related in some way to Lucius Aelius, as Aviania here is the wife of Publius Aelius. The same type of stone is used for both inscriptions, but the engraver of the two inscriptions is different as the letter forms are clearly different. The text belongs to the first or earlier second century AD.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645646

Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.17

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